

From Bucharest to Washington: Suveranist positions toward the climatic agenda in the presidential campaigns

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Abstract

This study examines how climate policies are presented in the electoral programs of sovereigntist candidates in the 2024 Romanian presidential elections, by comparison to those of Donald Trump in the 2024 U.S. elections. In Romania, climate policies follow the framework of the European Green Deal, whereas in the United States they are associated with the Green New Deal and the Inflation Reduction Act. Through a comparative approach, the study highlights transnational alignments in sovereigntist discourse on climate policies. The research strategy is qualitative, employing document analysis and comparative analysis as methods. The findings indicate that climate policies are included in the programs under review and are instrumentalized as a campaign issue in both Romania and the U.S., frequently being countered by the proposals advanced by sovereigntist candidates. The conclusions reveal that climate policies acquire the function of consolidating political agendas and collective identities within the electoral platforms of sovereigntist candidates in both Romania and the United States.

Keywords

European Green Deal; Green New Deal; climate sovereignty; presidential elections; climate policies

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Introduction

In December 2019, European Commission President Ursula von der Leyen announced the European Green Deal, one of the six priorities of the European Commission for the period 2019-2024. The European Green Deal is the successor to the Europe 2020 Strategy, aiming for innovative, sustainable, and inclusive growth. As initially conceived, the new package of measures proposed to build "a society with a modern, resource-efficient and competitive economy, with net-zero greenhouse gas emissions in 2050 and where economic growth is decoupled from resource use" (European Commission, 2019). The new strategy set two measurable headline targets: a 55% reduction in emissions by 2030 and achieving climate neutrality by 2050. To achieve the 2030 target, the 2021 Commission proposed a package of new and revised legislation, known as 'Fit for 55', including 13 interconnected revised laws and six legislative proposals on climate and energy (European Commission, 2021). The European Green Deal was intended to be a unifying solution to Europe's multiple crises, including the economic recovery from the pandemic, climate change, high energy dependence on Russia, and competition for net-zero emission technologies from China and the US (UNIDO, 2020). The European strategy to reduce dependence on Russian fossil fuels, *REPowerEU*, also underscores the importance of decarbonization, particularly in terms of renewable energy deployment and energy savings (European Commission, 2022). However, the current social and political challenges that Europe has faced and is facing, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, Russia's war of aggression against Ukraine, the energy crisis and the increasing cost of living, the rise of the far-right force at the European and national levels, have determined a reorientation of the strategy to the new circumstances, arousing different opinions among epistemic communities or decision-makers, and adding a series of particularities to the decisions that will have to be made, but also to the medium and long-term perspectives (Ciot, 2023).

The Green New Deal (GND) is defined in H.Res.109 (2019), a framework resolution that proposes a 10-year mobilization towards net-zero emissions, well-paid jobs, investments in infrastructure, and climate justice. It is not a law per se, but a normative and prospective framework (Congress.gov, 2019). In practice, some of the ambitious goals of the GND have been realized in the Inflation Reduction Act (IRA, 2022), a package of tax credits and "technology-neutral" investments in clean energy, grids, and industry (Rhodium Group, 2022, 2023). Independent assessments estimate that the IRA could lead the US to be 32% to 42% below 2005 levels in 2030, which is below the 50–52% target, but significantly below the no-IRA scenario (Rhodium Group, 2022, 2023; REPEAT Project, 2022).

European and American repositionings towards climate policies, primarily driven by the opposition of the extreme right, have become significant in the context of the 2024 presidential elections in Romania and the United States. This study examines the representation of the European Green Deal and the Green New Deal (USA) in the electoral programs of the sovereigntist candidates in Romania (Călin Georgescu and George Simion), as well as in the program of the presidential candidate Donald Trump. The scientific approach starts from two research questions: How do sovereigntist candidates in the 2024 Romanian presidential elections position themselves in relation to climate policies, compared to the approach of Donald Trump in the 2024 U.S. presidential elections? What are the common elements in the programs of the three candidates regarding climate policies?

The research is structured in six sections: an introductory section that presents the general framework of the topic addressed, a section dedicated to reviewing the specialized literature, followed by the research design and methodology, including the research questions and the methods used in the research, the section dedicated to the results and their interpretation, through which the program of each candidate chosen for the present research is analyzed individually, followed by discussions regarding the identification of typical elements of the analyzed programs and conclusions.

Literature review

Recent literature describes the European Green Deal as an EU growth and security strategy. However, it is being implemented in a more nuanced political and geopolitical context than it was in 2019. The war in Ukraine accelerated the security argument (energy, industry, raw materials). At the same time, the rise of right-wing populist-radical parties shifted the controversy from climate change denial to contesting the instruments (ETS, standards, CBAM) through narratives about costs, competitiveness and sovereignty (Lockwood and Lockwood, 2022; Ćetković and Hagemann, 2020; Bocquillon, 2024). Analyses indicate that the European Green Deal remains feasible if it strengthens its pillars of equity, competitiveness, and security, without compromising the decarbonization targets (Dupont, 2024; Oberthür and von Homeyer, 2023).

Studies show that radical right-wing parties no longer target climate science, but rather policy design, presenting the transition as a burden on "ordinary people," agriculture, and the automotive industry (Lockwood and Lockwood, 2022; Ćetković and Hagemann, 2020). Analyses document three recurring tactics: politicization along identity/nationalist lines; cultural reframing of decarbonization as "punitive"; and gradual institutional dismantling by diluting or postponing instruments (Yazar and Haarstad, 2023).

The wave of agricultural protests in 2023-2024 in the European Union crystallized the term "greenlash". It highlighted vulnerabilities on the social-distributive side: perceptions of net costs, anxiety about competitiveness, and agricultural incomes. Recent research recommends a "course correction" by increasing targeted compensation, access to technology, and positive narratives for farmers, without disarming climate goals (Chapron, 2024; Finger, 2024; Bocquillon, 2024).

The energy security literature presents a shift from a "liberal" framework of external energy policy to a strategic one, driven by the war on the EU's borders and the need for energy independence. The strategic framework encompasses accelerated diversification of sources, efficiency, electrification, RES, grids, hydrogen, and a diplomacy of critical raw materials (Siddi and Kustova, 2021; Herranz-Surrallés, 2024). The REPowerEU package is interpreted as an acceleration of the European Green Deal's trajectory, rather than a change of direction, by increasing objectives and redistributing investments (Bocquillon, 2024; Oberthür and von Homeyer, 2023). Studies highlight tensions regarding the cost of capital, the pace of electrification, and resilience to climate variability (Boitier et al., 2023; De Felice et al., 2023).

In the medium term, resilience depends on investments in networks and flexibility, as well as the industrial uptake of new technologies and the reduction of emerging dependencies in clean technology chains. In the absence of a coordinated industrial policy, the risks of lock-in and fragmentation of the internal market (through non-harmonized national support schemes) increase (Herranz-Surrallés, 2024; Dupont, 2024).

Regarding CBAM, which aims to correct carbon leakage and level the carbon price between domestic production and imports, research anticipates heterogeneous effects across sectors and partners, with winners/losers and possible trade tensions, but also the existence of a potential for climate policy diffusion (Leturcq, 2022; Jakob, 2023; Yang et al., 2024; Amendola et al., 2025; Otto, 2025). The recurring recommendation is to anchor CBAM in carbon diplomacy and in the use of revenues for just transitions.

Despite the greenlash, public support for climate action remains overwhelming, provided that the cost distribution is fair and tangible benefits are evident (lower bills, jobs, and clean air) (Panarello and Gatto, 2023). Studies of the GND in the US have shown that the initiative serves as an "umbrella framework," linking decarbonization to social justice, job creation, and infrastructure, thereby shifting

the political agenda (Galvin and Healy, 2020; Boyle et al., 2021; Green, 2024). However, public perceptions remain strongly polarized, both along partisan lines and along urban/rural and sectoral divides (Carmack et al., 2022; McConnell, 2023). Media and messaging analyses reveal that label and framing effects can either increase or decrease support for similar policy packages, even when the content remains constant (Bhatti, 2022; Stokes and Warshaw, 2017). GND proposes massive public investments in decarbonization, accompanied by job creation and a reduction in inequality, thereby embedding decarbonization in a logic of inclusive growth and justice (Galvin and Healy, 2020; Boyle et al., 2021). Public policy studies show that this explicit linking of climate goals to social benefits (housing, health, infrastructure) has shifted the focus of the debate away from classic carbon pricing instruments towards "investment packages" (Konisky and Carley 2021; Green 2022). This results in a dual perception: for supporters, the GND is a strategy for economic and climate security; for critics, a costly or even "productivist" agenda framed in Green Keynesianism (Mastini et al., 2021; Green, 2022; Andreucci et al., 2025).

A robust consensus in the literature indicates that the label "Green New Deal" serves as a partisan cue, as its mere mention reduces support for the same policy package among specific segments, particularly in rural areas, compared to a neutral description (McConnell, 2023). In surveys and experiments, support increases when the emphasis is on local benefits, jobs, and public health, without using the partisan label (Stokes and Warshaw, 2017; Gazmararian et al., 2025). Electoral analyses show that while the GND mobilizes the progressive base, it does not uniformly penalize Democratic candidates (Carmack et al., 2022). A significant part of the GND's perception derives from its ability to build coalitions between climate movements, affected communities, and labor unions. Interviews and qualitative studies highlight a variety of strategies, ranging from "green growth" to GND approaches, which call for public investment, labor standards, and plans for fossil fuel-dependent regions (Sicotte, 2022; Basseches et al., 2022). Local cases demonstrate that projects with visible benefits for workers and communities increase acceptance, whereas projects perceived as imposed "from above" tend to strengthen opposition (Grabowski et al., 2023; Carley, Engle, and Konisky 2021). Studies also indicate that a GND narrative focused on reducing inequities (air quality, green spaces, energy efficiency in housing) increases support, especially in disadvantaged communities (Allam, 2024). In the area of housing, the "Green New Deal for Public Housing" approaches rearticulate perceptions, shifting from costs to health, comfort, and job benefits, when associated with stable financing and tenant involvement (Cummings, 2022; Galvin and Healy, 2020).

There is evidence that GND packages are received differently depending on the institutional and economic context of the states. Systematic reviews highlight that, despite polarization, many states adopt GND policies (investment and justice) when there are broad coalitions and clear local benefits (Basseches et al., 2022; Boyle et al., 2021). At the same time, scholars note tensions between the "productivism" of some versions of GND and the imperatives of equity/justice, tensions that are reflected in public perceptions (Mastini et al., 2021; Levidow, 2020).

Criticisms range from fiscal feasibility to the risk of reproducing "productivist" logics or marginalizing communities if justice is not operationalized (Mastini et al., 2021; Ajl, 2021; Andreucci et al., 2025). On the other hand, comparative reviews indicate that versions prioritizing equity and public investment can support a broader coalition and positive perceptions, provided they are accompanied by tangible local benefits and genuine public participation (Green, 2024; Basseches et al., 2022).

Partisan labels, media framing, and the distribution of benefits shape public perceptions of GND. Three directions for strengthening legitimacy are suggested: (1) emphasis on tangible local benefits and health/jobs narratives (Stokes and Warshaw, 2017; Beland, 2024); (2) coalitions with

unions and communities, with precise "just transition" mechanisms (Sicotte, 2022; Basseches et al., 2022); (3) avoiding the labeling trap by communicating concrete content and outcomes, not just political branding (McConnell, 2023; Carmack et al., 2022). In this sense, GND remains a framework capable of reorienting perceptions when it explicitly links to economic security, public health, and equity, and when it demonstrates its effects at the community scale (Green, 2024; Boyle et al., 2021; Galvin and Healy, 2020).

In the specialized literature that analyses the topic of this study, research is almost non-existent. However, the presence of research that can create the interpretive frameworks for the topic addressed is reported – some of them analyze climate "skepticism" in Romania, offering typologies and discursive frameworks suitable for deciphering the anti-"Green Deal"/"European Green Pact"/messages (Vulpe, 2020); others discuss Romania's administrative capacity to implement the Green Deal, which is helpful as a background for internal discursive tensions (Ciot, 2021). Some studies analyze how AUR's anti-EU appeals influence Euroscepticism, a helpful phenomenon for understanding the "anti-Brussels" framework in which the Green Deal/European Green Pact is also placed (Stoica and Voina, 2023), and others discuss the "ecology" of the extreme right and geopolitical resentments, including references to the AUR and the Romanian framework (Mihai and Ungureanu, 2024). Authors such as Witajewska-Baltvilka et.al (2024) address the "politicization" of green rhetoric in Central and Eastern Europe, providing a context for the reception of the European Green Deal in the region (including Romania).

Analyzing President Donald Trump's electoral platform during the election campaign, specialized articles focusing on the Green New Deal issue are present, but in limited numbers. Some scholars discuss the "key election of 2024" for climate/energy and document the use by (re)elected President Donald Trump of the "green new scam" framework, as well as the repositioning of the campaign in terms of global costs/trust, while others analyze the electoral victory and the climate crisis, focusing on how the rhetoric of "costly green policies" and anti-Green Deal was used for electoral mobilization and an anti-regulation agenda (Faber, 2024). Gounaridis and Newell (2024) address the "social anatomy of climate change denial" in the US and the psycho-political mechanisms (identity-protective cognition) that explain why "the Republican public positively receives Green New Scam" messages. Other studies conduct a comparative rhetorical analysis of US presidential climate programs, identifying the framing strategies and persuasive appeals used by Trump, which align with the "anti-Green Deal" branding (Pandey, 2024). The epistemic community critically approaches the discourse (CDA) on the 2024 campaign, highlighting the emotional appeals, identity frames, and agenda control strategies relevant to labelling green policies as "scams" (Hamed and Alqurashi, 2025). Finally, some research shows how nationalist rhetoric fuels climate polarization in the US, with case studies and references to the program presented by Trump (Schertzer and Wood, 2025).

In view of this, the analysis proposed by the study complements the existing specialized literature and, especially, the Romanian specialized literature, opening a new research direction.

Research design and methodology

The paper aims to analyze the impact of the rise of far-right forces at the European and national levels on the rhetoric behind the European Green Deal and the way it will be altered in this new political configuration. The study will begin by examining the current state of discussions on the European Green Deal and the American Green New Deal. It will then demonstrate how the far-right force at the European and international levels attacks this strategy and, implicitly, climate policies. The study examines the sovereigntist positions on climate policies in Romania and the USA, as reflected in the

electoral programs of the sovereigntist candidates in Romania and in Trump's program, aiming to identify commonalities in both the candidates' positioning and their programs.

Thus, the research questions from which the scientific approach starts are: How do sovereigntist candidates in the 2024 Romanian presidential elections position themselves in relation to climate policies, compared to Trump's approach in the 2024 U.S. presidential elections? 2. What are the common elements in the programs of the three candidates regarding climate policies?

Research methodology. The methodological approach of the research is qualitative, using document analysis and comparative analysis as methods, applied to the electoral programs of the following candidates: the independent candidate Călin Georgescu, with the electoral program *Food, Water, Energy: A Return to the Roots of the Romanian Nation*; the candidate of AUR, George Simion, with the electoral program *Planul Simion - Reconstruim Romania*; and, for the USA, Donald Trump, with the electoral program, promoted under the umbrella of *Agenda 47* and, politically, reflected almost entirely in the Republican GOP platform.

According to the official website of Călin Georgescu (<https://calingeorgescu.ro/program/>), the electoral program *Hrană, Apă, Energie: O întoarcere la rădăcinile neamului românesc (Food, Water, Energy: A return to the roots of the Romanian nation)* "was proposed to the Romanian people since 2010 and has undergone changes over the years to respond to the great challenges of the present" (Georgescu, 2024). There is no record for the specific date for the official launch of this program.

The electoral program *Planul Simion – Reconstruim Romania (Simion Plan - We Rebuild Romania)* was launched on June 27, 2024, following the announcement of the candidacy on June 18, 2024. The document analyzed in this study comes from Simion's webpage (<https://georgesimion.ro/wp-content/uploads/2024/11/Planul-Simion-Reconstruim-Romania.pdf>).

Agenda 47, Donald Trump's electoral platform, was launched on December 15, 2022, and is available on the candidate's website at <https://www.donaldjtrump.com/platform>. This electoral platform formed the conceptual basis of the Republican Party Platform for the presidential election, the latter institutionalizing and formalizing, at party level, the main directions previously stated by the candidate. The document entitled *2024 GOP Platform. Make America Great Again*, comes from the web source <https://prod-static.gop.com/media/RNC2024-Platform.pdf>.

The investigation period of the study covers the pre-campaign and campaign stages of the 2024 presidential elections in Romania, as well as those of the 2024 elections in the United States.

Results and interpretation

This section is dedicated to analyzing the electoral programs with a focus on identifying the positioning of sovereigntist candidates toward climate policies.

Călin Georgescu's program. Independent candidate Călin Georgescu was the surprise candidate in the first round of the Romanian presidential elections. We analyze his program (*Hrană, Apă, Energie: O întoarcere la rădăcinile neamului românesc (HAE)/ Food, Water, Energy: A Return to the Roots of the Romanian Nation (HAE)*), in relation to the European Green Deal.

The program positions itself as a project of "sovereignty-distributism" with "participatory democracy". It emphasizes the "worker-owner economy," cooperativization, popular banks, and local markets. It explicitly formulates fiscal policy targets (10% flat rate, 2% turnover tax over €1 million), as well as the redirection of EU funds to the "small owner". Another central statement defines the program as "Christianity applied to the real economy", the HAE triad being described as "harmony between God, Man, and Nature". The document supports organic farming, the replacement of synthetic pesticides with "ecological variants", considers rivers "sacred places", and solar/wind energy

only "supplementary", "far from being a serious alternative" to oil, coal and gas. In short, HAE combines an axiological sovereignty with pro-local, pro-SME economic interventions and a "moralization" of the economy. (Georgescu, 2024).

Georgescu bases his proposal on a set of ethical-spiritual and community values: "re-sovereignization of the person" through small and medium-sized productive property, "brotherhood", "love of neighbor", re-professionalization, local management, local markets, and cooperativism. The program openly states that the economic side cannot be separated from the social side and proposes "restoring the Christian vision in the economy". This axiological charge is articulated through a project to re-engage local communities as a driving force of development: an economy of producers, not speculation, with participatory mechanisms in public decision-making (Georgescu, 2024). The European Green Deal, on the other hand, is a technocratic and multi-sectoral strategy, anchored in law (EU Climate Law) and in measurable targets. It does not operate with confessional premises; instead, it mobilizes regulation, standards and investments as levers to retrain the market (ETS, CBAM), support the energy transition (RED III) and reform the food system (Farm to Fork), in sync with dedicated funds for social equity (JTM, SCF). If HAE proposes a localist moralization of the economy, the European Green Deal proposes a structural transformation. From this opposition emerge a significant portion of the convergences and divergences that we will present below.

In terms of economic and fiscal policies, HAE provides for a flat rate of 10%, a 2% tax on turnover over 1 million RON (simplified collection), stimulating the economy to the detriment of consumption, strengthening small producers, popular banks, cooperatives and "participatory economic democracy" (worker-owners). The "redirection of EU funds to small owners" is targeted, explicitly mentioned in the program summary. The European Green Deal alters incentives through carbon pricing (ETS and the extension of ETS2 to buildings/transport), standards (automotive CO₂, EED, and RED III), CBAM (the allocation of a carbon price to imports), and conditionalities in financing (from NextGenerationEU to JTM/SCF). The European Green Deal does not have a unitary fiscal model for MS but creates frameworks and allocates funds for green investments and just transition. The central thesis is to replace "dirty" capital with "clean" capital through targeted regulation and subsidies, not through changes in ownership. (European Commission, 2021; EU, 2023e).

Even though both programs claim to mobilize EU funds, the significant difference lies in the recipients of these funds and the financing conditions. While HAE views the "small owner" as the recipient, preferring massive redirections to local farms/enterprises, the European Green Deal aims to achieve green objectives and social equity through green/efficiency criteria, competitive mechanisms, and national planning.

From the point of view of agriculture and its purpose of producing food, HAE emphasizes the importance of organic agriculture, replacing synthetic pesticides with organic alternatives, supporting beekeeping, restoring the "dignity" of the farmer-producer, cooperatization, local markets, local processing industry, "land values". The program outlines an agro-ecology with a spiritual and traditionalist touch, which prioritizes short supply chains and the "cleanliness" of ecosystems. The European Green Deal, through the Farm to Fork program, sets quantitative targets at the EU level, including a 50% reduction in the use and risk of pesticides by 2030, a decrease in fertilizer consumption, reaching a threshold of 25% of land occupied by organic agriculture and a reduction in antimicrobials in animal husbandry.

Both the HAE and the European Green Deal propose "clean food" as a central element; however, although there is alignment of direction, only the EGD operates with quantified targets and EU mechanisms, while the HAE anchors the same direction in an ethical, spiritual, and sovereigntist

framework. The HAE gives priority to local and community production as a "universal solution". The EGD assumes frictions, such as farmer protests or political adjustments, but remains on track with its objectives. In contrast, the HAE assumes a massive transfer of resources to small producers, with the risk of straining internal market rules if the conditionality deviates from the *acquis communautaire*. (Georgescu, 2024).

Regarding the water issue, an essential element in the program, HAE sees water as a national common good and a pillar of public health. The document discusses water quality ("free of toxic chemical residues"), the relationship between water, health, and agriculture, the cleanliness of water basins, and the importance of clean soil. The tone of the document is normative and civic, evoking the "sacredness" of water as a cultural norm (Georgescu, 2024). The European Green Deal does not have a separate "Water pillar", but Farm to Fork and biodiversity aim at pollution reduction, ecosystem services and restoration. EU standards for drinking water and wastewater remain essential elements for EU policies. A common point between HAE and the European Green Deal is the reduction of chemical load, which HAE places in a cultural-axiological register, and EGD in a technical-normative register with indicators and reporting.

The most striking differences appear in the field of energy. HAE recognizes solar and wind energy only as additional sources, "far from being a serious alternative" to oil, coal and gas. The emphasis falls on energy security and on the criticism of the "permanent energy crisis" attributed to the "indiscriminate adoption of green policies". HAE envisages "cheap and abundant energy, especially unconventional", without clearly defining this notion, however. The message is pragmatic-sovereigntist, aiming at stability and low prices as primary objectives, considering "green" policies as problematic for Romania. On the other hand, in 2023 the European Green Deal raised the renewable energy target to at least 42.5% by 2030, setting a clear direction for accelerating the use of renewables, electrification, efficiency, and interconnections. (European Commission, 2023b). While HAE assumes maintaining fossil fuels as a core element, minimizing the role of wind/solar to a complementary status, the European Green Deal maximizes the importance of wind and solar energy and the gradual withdrawal of fossils. In addition, the EU internalizes carbon at the border, which means that fossil-dependent industries will face increasing cost pressures, including in Romania.

In terms of governance and financing, HAE proposes a model of participatory democracy (legislative initiatives directly from citizens), simplification of regulations, "resizing the political and administrative system", fiscal stability, and especially mutual institutions (popular banks, cooperatives), seen as the infrastructure of the worker-owner economy. Regarding European financing, the document calls for "redirecting EU funds to the small owner" and "collection and processing centers" in local networks. The European Green Deal anchors governance in EU frameworks (national plans, reporting, indicators), with targeted funds, the implementation of which depends on administrative capacity, co-financing and conditionality.

In practice, HAE uses the European Green Deal and the EU policy/funding ecosystem in three ways. One way is at the rhetorical level, proposing an alternative identity to "Brussels" with an emphasis on localism, sovereignty, and spirituality. However, HAE translates part of the European Green Deal objectives into popular language (clean food, clean water, communities), capitalizing on the popularity of the "food-water-energy" topics. This "nationalization" of sustainability objectives makes them digestible for a public skeptical of the "green technocracy". A second way is found at the financial level, as HAE claims EU money ("redirecting funds"), exploiting the European Green Deal/NextGenEU framework to finance local infrastructure (collection/processing centers, cooperatives, capitalization of small producers).

At the doctrinal level, a third approach to exploiting the European Green Deal is identified. HAE adopts specific objectives of the European Green Deal (eco-agriculture, reduction of chemicals) and rejects others (accelerating wind/solar as a "serious alternative"), leading to a politicized rhetoric, which claims the merits of an "authentic" green agriculture (in the traditionalist key), while criticizing the rapid energy transition on cost/security grounds.

Table 1. Dimensions of the HAE vision compared to the European Green Deal.

Dimension	HAE (Calin Georgescu)	European Green Deal
Vision	Sovereignty-distributism, applied Christianity, participatory democracy, worker-owner economy.	Technocratic green growth strategy, 2030/2050 climate targets, carbon internalization
Food	"Clean" agro-ecology, short chains, cooperatization, anti-pesticides	Farm to Fork: -50% pesticides/risk, 25% organic, targets N and antibiotics
Water	"Common good", purity, "holy places", chemical bans	EU Directives + F2F effects (pollution reduction, biodiversity, restoration)
Energy	Fossils as base; solar/wind only additional; "cheap/abundant energy"	RED III: ≥42.5% renewables 2030; electrification; ETS/CBAM; efficiency
Fiscality	Flat rate 10%, 2% on turnover >1 million €, incentive to earn	No single EU tax scheme; levers: ETS/CBAM/standards/subsidies
Financing	Redirecting EU funds to the smallholder	JTM/SCF/RRF, green/social conditionalities, national plans
Governance	Simplification, mutual institutions, and citizen legislative initiative	EU plans, indicators, procedures, monitoring and reporting

Concluding this program, it is evident that Georgescu's program translates the green landscape into a popular and national language. Regarding food and water, convergence with the European Green Deal is evident at the level of objectives (agro-ecology, chemical reduction, public health), not necessarily at the level of implementation modalities. Energy remains the area of divergence. The European Green Pact calls for the acceleration of renewables and electrification, while the HAE advocates for prudence based on security/prices. The HAE capitalizes on the distrust of the "green technocracy" and converts it into a pro-community narrative. The HAE and the European Green Pact are not entirely antagonistic. On dimensions such as food and water, there are apparent convergences; however, on the energy dimension, a rupture in vision occurs.

George Simion's program. George Simion, AUR's presidential candidate, proposed to the electorate, before the first round of the presidential elections in Romania, an electoral program entitled *Planul Simion - Reconstruim Romania/Simion Plan - Rebuild Romania*. It represents a political offer centered on economic and energy sovereignty, the active role of the state in the market, and a pronounced focus on energy security. The document proposes, among others, the preservation/restart of coal-fired capacities, the expansion of gas (CCGT), the acceleration of hydro (including Tarnița-Lăpușești) and the completion of units 3 & 4 at Cernavodă, accompanied by an explicit rhetoric of "renegotiation" of the Green Deal and the PNRR "at the points where they affect the interests of Romanians" (Simion, 2024: 8-9, 22-25).

This positioning comes into tension with the architecture of the European Green Deal, legally established by the European Climate Law (Reg. (EU) 2021/1119), which sets climate neutrality in 2050 and an intermediate objective of at least -55% by 2030, implemented through the "Fit for 55" package (European Commission, 2021). In the Simion Plan, the fundamental rupture with the European Green

Deal is formulated openly: "we will renegotiate [...] Green Deal", and in the energy chapter, both the European legislation on decarbonization and the effects of the Natura 2000 regime on hydropower are identified as "challenges" (Simion, 2024: 8-9, 21-23). This language shifts the center of gravity from alignment to resistance: the European Green Deal becomes a technical-legal obstacle that would slow down the valorization of national resources and impose economic costs. In contrast, the EU framework assumes that the transformation is systemic and requires common rules (from ETS2 to automotive standards and RED III) to avoid free-riding and market fragmentation (European Commission, 2021; DG CLIMA, 2024).

The most visible divergence concerns fossil fuels. Candidate George Simion's program stipulates "we keep the coal-fired production capacities in Rovinari and Turceni functional" and "we finalize the works on the gas-fired power plants in Iernut and Brăila; we build new CCGT capacities in Ișalnița, Turceni, Mintia" – with a declarative target of over 10,000 MW net available (Simion, 2024: 22). In the logic of the European Green Deal, coal has an accelerated exit schedule, and the role of gas is transitional, not long-term expansion, especially in the electricity sector, which must decarbonize first (EU, 2021; EU, 2023a). Structural expansions on gas risk "lock-in" of emissions and long-lived assets, difficult to reconcile with 2050 neutrality.

The second significant divergence is the use of hydropower in sensitive areas. The plan prioritizes completing the "almost ready" projects (Răstolnița, Bumbesti, Dumitra, Surduc) and the Tarnița-Lăpușești storage development, denouncing "pseudo-ecological protests" and claiming that Natura 2000 has reduced the development potential (Simion, 2024: 24-25). However, the European Green Deal treats biodiversity as a co-equal pillar of the transition (not as a brake), and the new Nature Restoration Regulation introduces binding targets by 2030/2050 (EU, 2024). This does not mean that hydro or storage are undesirable in the EU; it means that they must be designed and operated in a way that avoids habitat degradation, with assessments, mitigation and, where appropriate, alternatives.

On road transport, Simion's program does not formulate an explicit trajectory for compliance with CO₂ standards for passenger cars. In the European Green Deal, this pillar is crucial. By amending Regulation (EU) 2019/631 in 2023, a reduction to 0 g CO₂/km for new cars by 2035 was confirmed, with intermediate steps in place until 2030 (EU, 2023c; DG CLIMA, 2024). Without a clear national path (including charging infrastructure, incentives, and industry), Romania risks compliance gaps and subsequent greater pressures on producers, consumers, and the grid.

Another point of friction is the design of the energy market. The plan proposes a much more interventionist role for the state: "we eliminate the monopoly of utility supply and involve the state as a 'player' in the energy market", structural separations between distribution and supply and even "temporary bans on the export of some resources" (Simion, 2024: 22). The EU internal energy market relies on interconnections, standard rules, signal prices, and the compatibility of state aid with climate objectives. Discretionary interventions (e.g., export restrictions) may contravene the single market framework and increase the risk of litigation or conditional financing. In addition, regulatory predictability is a key criterion for mobilizing the private capital needed for the transition (European Commission, 2021).

In terms of narrative, the document explicitly denounces the "pseudo-ecological impossibility". It qualifies the Green Deal as a "dictation" and an "ideological totem", suggesting that decarbonization would distort the link between economic activity and climate change (Simion, 2024: 31). The European Green Deal, however, draws its legitimacy from legislatively adopted objectives (the Climate Law, RED III, EED) and from market instruments (ETS/ETS2) precisely to internalize the external costs of emissions, not to substitute economics with ideology (EU, 2021; EU, 2023a; EU, 2023b; DG CLIMA,

2024). The difference in vocabulary is not cosmetic: it organizes the political field between “sovereignty and price” (George Simion Plan) and “decarbonization compatible with competitiveness” (European Green Deal).

However, there are fundamental points of convergence. First, it is about storage. The candidate program prioritizes Tarnița-Lăpușești, recognizing that without storage, RES integration remains limited and the SEN vulnerable (Simion, 2024: 24–25). The European Green Deal, through RED III and network instruments, aims to achieve precisely this extension of system flexibility (storage, demand management, digitalization) to support electrification and the massive integration of renewables. Provided that the design is compatible with Natura 2000, Tarnița would serve as a “bridge” between the two key objectives: national energy security and decarbonization (EU, 2023a).

Table 2. Dimensions of the vision of the Simion Plan, compared to the European Green Deal

Dimension	Rebuild Romania (George Simion)	European Green Deal
Energy vision	Security by maintaining coal, expanding gas, accelerating hydro, nuclear 3&4; SMR caution.	Neutrality 2050; fossil phase-down; RES/storage/grid acceleration; opening to nuclear with conditions.
Climate targets	It does not formulate explicit national targets aligned with the 2030/2050 goals.	At least –55% by 2030; net-zero by 2050 (Climate Law).
Coal	Maintaining Rovinari/Turceni as a reserve/functional in the medium term.	Accelerated exit; tightened ETS; gradual closure.
Natural gas	Completing Iernut/Brăila; new CCGT (Ișalnița, Turceni, Mintia).	Limited transition role; avoid long-term lock-in.
Nuclear	Priority Cernavodă 3 & 4; caution towards SMR.	Admitted to taxonomy with conditions; may contribute to decarbonization.
Hydro & storage	Completion of blocked projects; CHEAP Tarnița; criticism of Natura 2000 barriers.	Sustained storage, but compatible with biodiversity and nature restoration.
Biomass & waste	Expansion (pyrolysis/gasification, biodegradable fraction, low-value wood).	Strict RED III criteria; priority of circular economy.
Prosumers & efficiency	Declared support; orientation towards local solutions.	“Energy efficiency first”, acceleration of prosumers and distributed RES.
Road transport	No explicit trajectory for CO ₂ standards.	CO ₂ standards for vehicles (0 g CO ₂ /km from 2035) + infrastructure.
Energy market	Interventionism: player state, separations, and possible export restrictions.	Integrated internal market, standard rules, price signals for decarbonization.
Biodiversity	Criticism of “pseudo-ecology” and the constraints of Natura 2000.	Co-equal pillar (Biodiversity Strategy, Nature Restoration Regulation).
Financing	Reorientation of PNRR; preference for national investments.	EGD compliance conditionality; EIB/EU funds mobilization.
Governance	Renegotiation of EGD/PNRR on the points considered harmful.	Mandatory transposition of the acquis; Commission-state dialogue.

Secondly, the convergence concerns nuclear energy. The candidate program supports the completion of Cernavodă 3 & 4, although it is cautious about SMR (Simion, 2024: 22). In the EU taxonomy, nuclear energy is eligible under certain conditions. On the 2030/2050 trajectory, new nuclear capacities can make a significant contribution to reducing the carbon intensity of the energy mix. Here, the convergence is more practical than ideological: the issue becomes one of financing, timing, and governance of the project, rather than a climate principle (EU, 2021).

Thirdly, convergence is observed in terms of efficiency, prosumers, and geothermal energy. The candidate's program supports local solutions, and the European Green Deal, through EED and RED III, places efficiency precisely at the heart of its strategy ("energy efficiency first") and facilitates distributed generation. With well-calibrated policies (predictable support schemes, modernization of distribution networks, protection of vulnerable consumers), these areas can become spaces of co-benefits: lower bills, local jobs, reduced emissions (UE, 2023a; EU, 2023b). Finally, Simion's program denounces the "decoupling" between social reality and climate policies, emphasizing price and jobs. This is a legitimate criticism if it refers to implementation (rent capture, poorly designed projects, lack of protection for vulnerable consumers). However, the instruments of the European Green Deal include just transition mechanisms and social mitigation funds (including the Social Climate Fund) to amortize the costs of the transition (EU, 2023b).

Concluding, the Simion Plan - Rebuild Romania proposes a change of roles: the state returns to being the central actor, and energy becomes the pivot of reindustrialization. In this grammar, the European Green Deal is problematized and called for renegotiation.

Donald Trump's 2024 election platform. President Donald Trump's 2024 election platform, promoted under the *Agenda 47* umbrella and, politically, reflected almost entirely in the GOP 2024 Republican platform, treats the Green New Deal (GND) as a "total enemy". Key messages are "ending the Socialist Green New Deal", "DRILL, BABY, DRILL", "Energy Independent / Energy Dominant", plus the promise to "repeal the electric vehicle mandate".

Table 3. Dimensions of President Trump's program vision compared to the Green New Deal

Dimension	Donald Trump's electoral program	Green New Deal (SUA)
Vision	"Unleash American Energy", "Energy Dominant", cheap energy as an antidote to inflation.	10-year mobilization for net-zero, "jobs + climate", public health.
Climate targets	No explicit climate targets; focus on energy sovereignty.	Normative targets towards net-zero serve as an anchor for 2030/2050 trajectories.
Main narrative	Cost of living, "mandates" vs. "election", drilling/deregulation.	Climate crisis, climate justice, public investment.
The role of the state	Deregulation, leasing, relaxation of "permitting".	Investor/conductor state (tax credits, grants, standards).
Instruments	Repeal or relax EPA rules; redefine EV/clean incentives.	IRA incentives + standards; network expansion, electrification, efficiency.
Fossil regime	Oil/gas/coal expansion ("drill, baby, drill").	Accelerated fossil fuel phase-down.
Nuclear	Firm support	Compatible (in some versions), as a non-CO ₂ option.
Transport & vehicles	"Cancel the EV mandate"; re-evaluation of standards and stop/re-evaluation of EV funds.	Emission standards as leverage + incentives; charging infrastructure.
Networks & storage	Fast permitting, but with fossil priority; less central networks/storage.	Grids/storage are essential for RES integration and electrification.
Social	"Consumer rights" + jobs in traditional industries.	Just transition, protection for vulnerable communities.
Relation to GND	"Terminate the Socialist Green New Deal".	Umbrella framework for green transformation and equity.

The architecture of President Donald Trump's program shifts the focus from the "climate crisis" to the "cost of living" (Cama, 2024). The program's political strategy is based on three key pivots. The first is the link between energy and inflation, proposing "cheap energy" through drilling and deregulation versus "expense" attributed to green policies. A second pillar is the "Electric Vehicles" (EV) Mandate and the right to choose. The re-labelling of EPA (US Environmental Protection Agency) standards as "mandates" legitimizes their repeal as a form of market liberation (EPA 2024; Federal Register 2024). A third pillar is "Energy dominant", whereby the goal of energy dominance replaces the language of climate targets, and the emphasis falls on all-of-the-above (with fossil + nuclear as a priority) and accelerated permitting (Cama, 2024).

The fundamental differences with the GND are easy to map. While the GND/IRA pursues rapid decarbonization through incentives, standards, grids, and electrification, the Trump program prioritizes the exit from "mandates," the expansion of oil/gas/coal production, and the exemptions/simplifications of authorization. On transportation, the GND relies on performance standards and incentives for clean energy, while President Donald Trump's program translates these into an "EV mandate" and promises to repeal them. On electricity, the GND counts on the decline in the marginal cost of the clean mix and on grids, while President Donald Trump's program relies on fossil fuel supply to "cut" bills. On the social front, the GND advocates for climate justice, while President Donald Trump's program emphasizes the "consumer right" to choose cars/appliances, as well as jobs in traditional industries.

However, there are points of convergence. Nuclear energy is supported by President Donald Trump's program and, in some pro-decarbonization visions, remains a valid component of the non-CO₂ mix. Additionally, the idea of permitting reform has bipartisan potential if applied to grids/storage, not just fossil infrastructure.

In conclusion, President Donald Trump's program offers a coherent policy response for audiences concerned with prices and energy sovereignty. However, it does so by reframing the Green New Deal: from a framework for economic transformation towards zero emissions to a symbol of "mandates" and "costs." As such, the differences from the GND are structural: target (decarbonization vs. fossil fuel cheapening), instruments (incentives & standards vs. deregulation), transportation (standard vs. "EV mandate"), and mix (fossil phase-down vs. all-of-the-above). The possible bridge remains limited: nuclear, permitting for grids/storage, and maintaining incentives that have shown an effect in attracting private capital.

Discussion

Taken together, the messages and political programs of President Donald Trump, George Simion, and Călin Georgescu configure a family of positionings that reframe climate policies less as a climate mission and more as a matter of sovereignty, cost of living and national control of resources. Although they come from different institutional contexts (USA and Romania; party vs. candidate), convergences are visible: prioritizing energy independence/dominance, criticizing supranational "mandates" and regulations, emphasis on "cheap and abundant" energy and a preference for large projects (nuclear, hydro) as pillars of "energy security".

Three symbolic formulations coagulate the theme of sovereignty and "cheap energy". President Donald Trump's platform includes "Drill, baby, drill" and the promise of "Energy Independent, and even Dominant," while candidate George Simion's platform includes "energy sovereignty" and "regaining control over the gas, electricity, and hydro chains." Candidate Călin Georgescu's platform includes "cheap and abundant energy, especially unconventional." All these formulations shift the

spotlight from "climate" to "price/power/resilience," that is, immediate well-being and national control of resources.

Criticism of supra-national "green frameworks" and "mandates" appears in President Donald Trump's electoral program, which explicitly calls for "ending the Socialist Green New Deal" and the promise to "Cancel the Electric Vehicle Mandate", i.e. re-labelling federal emission standards as an unwanted "EV mandate". In Romania, candidate George Simion's program announces the "renegotiation of the Green Deal", which "affects the interests of Romanians" and signals Natura 2000 as a barrier to hydropower. In candidate Călin Georgescu's program, the discourse pivoted on sovereignty-distributism, which emphasizes the simplification of legislation and local decision-making, not on compliance with external targets and schemes.

"Cost of living" before "climate targets" is another common point of the candidates' programs. For President Donald Trump, the promise to reduce inflation by "unleashing American Energy", not by climate targets, is conveyed. For candidate George Simion, the energy chapter is introduced through prices and energy security, with an emphasis on the state's role and the completion of hydroelectric and nuclear projects. In contrast, for candidate Călin Georgescu, energy appears as a strategic input for reindustrialization and well-being, not as a tool for achieving a CO₂ target (Economica.net, 2024). All three subsume "green" in economic terms (price, invoice, jobs), not in numerically explicit decarbonization terms.

A reservation towards the rapid electrification of transportation (EV) is observed in all programs. At the federal level in the US, the EPA rule 2027–2032 is an emissions standard (technology-neutral, with multiple compliance paths), not a mandatory quota for EV sales. However, President Donald Trump's program politically refers to it as an "EV mandate" and promises to cancel it. In Romania, candidate George Simion does not build an explicit "anti-electrification", but treats EU decarbonization as a challenge, and his focus remains on hydro, gas and nuclear – that is, on security and price, not on accelerating EV. For candidate Călin Georgescu, transportation appears less normative and more in the logic of reindustrialization with "clean" technology, but an explicit trajectory for decarbonizing mobility is missing. The preference for the "big pillars" of the system, nuclear and hydro, is another common point among the analyzed programs. President Donald Trump's program proposes to "unleash Energy... including nuclear", candidate George Simion's clearly proposes the completion of Cernavodă 3 & 4 and Tarnița-Lăpușești as storage and system balancing, plus the list of "almost ready" hydropower plants to increase the flexibility and reserve of the system, and candidate Călin Georgescu's speaks of reindustrialization "on non-polluting technologies", "eco-efficiency" and organic agriculture, in a framework that favors "basic" infrastructure as a support for the real economy.

From the perspective of the political enterprise, all three programs employ the language of security (energy, economic) and national industry as justification for a shift in direction from the standard "green policies". In relation to "climate policies, the programs of President Donald Trump, candidate George Simion, and candidate Călin Georgescu share a language in which the state (or government) is called upon to provide cheap, secure energy through national control and large projects, while criticizing mandates and regulations perceived as exogenous or ideological.

Conclusions

The study analyzed how sovereigntist positions on climate policies are reflected in the electoral programs proposed by sovereigntist candidates in the 2024 Romanian presidential elections and by President Donald Trump in the USA.

Answering the first research question, regarding the positioning of the candidates with respect to climate policies, these three analyzed candidates share a standard matrix that foregrounds decision sovereignty, energy costs and basic infrastructure, and not decarbonization targets imposed "from outside". In this key, "green" is accepted only to the extent that it proves compatible with low prices, energy security, and national control over strategic resources. From here derive some significant similarities: the declared preference for the "heavy" pillars of the system, nuclear and hydro, as solutions capable of providing basic power, stability and autonomy; the skepticism towards "mandates" and standards considered excessive because they are perceived as instruments that increase costs for households and industry; the reorientation of the political language from the "climate crisis" towards the "cost of living" and "system resilience". In practical terms, this matrix yields a series of similar political options: support for large projects, tolerance or even support for the transitional role of gas, and a critical stance towards the acceleration of transport electrification when driven by rigid standards. However, unity of vision is not the same as an identity of agenda. President Donald Trump privileges deregulation and the boost of oil/gas offers in the name of "cheap energy," while candidate George Simion proposes a pronounced state interventionism in the energy market, and candidate Călin Georgescu emphasizes eco-efficiency and "public goods" (food, water, energy) within a framework of local decision-making and simple rules. Even so, the political outcome is comparable: decarbonization no longer drives policy design, but becomes conditioned by economic and security criteria, regulation is viewed with reserve, and infrastructure, predominantly nuclear and hydro-storage, becomes essential.

Answering the second research question, regarding the common elements in the programs of the three candidates in relation to climate policies, they outline common points despite the differences in institutional and geographical contexts, starting from the same axis: decisional sovereignty, cheap energy, and critical infrastructure ahead of decarbonization targets. Thus, the following common points stand out: the state must be able to decide the pace and composition of the transition without being constrained by targets imposed from the outside or by agencies that do not answer directly to the national electorate; nuclear as a zero-emission solution capable of providing baseload power and reducing external dependencies; appreciation of hydro for its dual role, of production and pumped storage; skepticism towards "mandates" and standards perceived as rigid, favoring the "choice" rule, through which people and companies should be able to opt for the technology and pace of adoption that suits them, and the state should not penalize options that are still popular; shifting the debate from the climate register to that of the cost of living and industry, preferring measures that promise to cushion price shocks; pronounced "infrastructureism", all three programs regarding investments in networks, storage, dispatchable production and system modernization as the key solution to the tensions between price, safety and environment; critical reporting to supranational frameworks, whether it is the Green New Deal in the United States or the European Green Deal and environmental directives in the EU. Therefore, the common elements in the programs of the three candidates can be summarized as an "energy security strategy" in which the climate does not disappear but moves down a level in the order of priorities. Sovereignty, price and infrastructure lead, and "green" remains accepted where it strengthens these three objectives.

The main contribution of the study is to highlight how climate policies, usually perceived as technical, become instruments of political and identity mobilization. At the same time, the research introduces a comparative Romania–USA perspective, revealing transnational convergences of sovereigntist discourse. Academically, the study complements the limited Romanian literature on the relationship between right-wing populism and the green transition. It also provides a framework for

interpreting the interactions between electoral programs and European or American climate policies. Additionally, it opens a research direction on the impact of Romanian political options on international negotiations. Through these contributions, the paper demonstrates that the elections in Romania cannot be understood only through the prism of the internal context, but also through geopolitical and thematic interdependencies.

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